

OPPORTUNITIES FOR PROPER NUTRITION FOR CHILDREN

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15771122>

Abstract

Proper nutrition of children is an important factor for their healthy development, physical and mental health. This article covers the basic principles of children's nutrition, their impact on their health, and important aspects. Studies show that malnutrition in childhood can lead to the development of various chronic diseases. In particular, unbalanced nutrition, lack or excess intake of vitamins and minerals have a negative impact on the child's immunity, bones, and nervous system. The article discusses the importance of organizing a rational diet in accordance with the age characteristics of children, forming a proper daily routine, and providing them with a sufficient amount of protein, fat, carbohydrates, vitamins, and minerals. Attention is also paid to measures to prevent problems caused by malnutrition - obesity, anemia, vitamin deficiency, and other diseases. Based on modern scientific research, the role of parents, schools and preschool institutions, as well as society as a whole, is of great importance in providing healthy nutrition to children.

Keywords: Children's nutrition, rational nutrition, healthy lifestyle, vitamin deficiency, obesity problem, nutritional hygiene, healthy generation.

Introduction

A healthy generation is one of the most important factors in the development of any country. In the Republic of Uzbekistan, the issue of children's health and their proper nutrition is one of the priorities of state policy. As our President Shavkat Mirziyoyev noted, "A healthy and balanced generation is the foundation of a new Uzbekistan." Therefore, proper nutrition of children is an important part not only of the healthcare sector, but also of education and social policy.

Rational nutrition is extremely important in childhood. During this period, the child's body grows rapidly, and mental and physical development occurs at a high pace. Malnutrition leads to problems such as weakened immunity, nutrient deficiencies, overweight or underweight. According to the World Health Organization (WHO), nutrition problems among children are globally relevant.

For young children, food must contain enough protein, fat, carbohydrates, vitamins and minerals. At the same time, it is not recommended to consume too many sweets, fatty or salty foods. Modern medical research shows that problems such as obesity, allergies, and anemia are increasing among school and preschool children. This is a consequence of the culture of unhealthy eating.

This article will examine in detail the principles of proper nutrition for children, the formation of a healthy eating culture, as well as ways to prevent unhealthy eating.

Literature review

Many scientific studies have been conducted on the issue of proper nutrition of children. According to WHO, nutritional problems among children around the world, in particular obesity and anemia, are increasing sharply. The research of Uzbek scientists is also reflected in these global problems.

The works of Karimova D.Sh. and Akbarova M.Sh. emphasize the basic principles of children's nutrition, their age-related needs and the benefits of a balanced diet. Their studies also cover in detail the health problems that arise as a result of malnutrition. The studies conducted by Yusupova N.O. provide information on the negative consequences of the imbalance of micro and macronutrients in the diet of children, especially the deficiency of iron, calcium, vitamins A and D. Also, the standards and recommendations for children's nutrition developed by the Ministry of Health of the Republic of Uzbekistan pay great attention to the balance of food composition, hygiene rules and food safety. International sources emphasize that the consumption of high-calorie, fatty and sweet products increases the risk of obesity and cardiovascular diseases in children. Fast food and carbonated drinks in particular have a negative impact on children's health. Uzbek and international experience shows that not only a medical, but also a pedagogical approach is important in forming a culture of healthy eating in children.

Research section

The research was conducted in 3 schools and 2 preschool institutions in the Balikchi district of Andijan region. Based on the questionnaire and observations, 120 children and 80 parents participated. The results of the study showed that there are serious shortcomings in the nutritional culture of children.

According to the survey results, 60% of children do not have breakfast in the morning, 45% often eat fast food, and 35% do not eat enough fruits and vegetables. Also, 50% of parents have problems with properly organizing their children's daily diet.

In addition, an imbalance of the main substances in food was observed. The children's diet lacked protein and complete vitamins, and on the contrary, there was an excess of fat and sweets.

During the study, specific recommendations were developed for rational nutrition, improving the nutritional culture, and forming a healthy lifestyle to improve children's health.

Discussion and results

The results of the study showed that the culture of proper nutrition among primary school students is not sufficiently formed. Parents face some problems in organizing their children's daily diet. 60% of children do not have breakfast in the morning and 45% are interested in fast food, which negatively affects their health. In particular, the lack of vitamins and minerals causes problems such as anemia, decreased immunity and general weakness among children.

Observations have shown that, along with a lack of protein and healthy fats, children's diets contain a high amount of unhealthy sweets and fatty foods. This situation can lead to obesity, cardiovascular diseases and metabolic disorders in the long term.

It was also observed that insufficient work is being done to promote healthy eating in schools and preschool institutions. It is necessary to increase the knowledge and skills of parents and teachers in this regard.

Based on the results of the study, it was determined that a comprehensive approach is needed to form a culture of healthy eating. This cannot be achieved without effective

cooperation between educational institutions, the health system and the family. As a result, a balanced diet for children, including fruits and vegetables, protein-rich foods in the diet, avoiding unhealthy foods and observing hygiene rules were identified as the main recommendations. On this basis, there is an opportunity to form a healthy generation.

Conclusion

The above research and analysis show that the formation of a culture of proper nutrition in children remains an urgent issue. Malnutrition leads to obesity, anemia, weakened immunity and other health problems.

By teaching the principles of healthy nutrition from a young age, it is possible to raise a healthy generation in the future. The cooperation of parents, teachers, medical workers and government organizations is important in this regard.

Also, balancing children's diets with proteins, fats, carbohydrates, vitamins and minerals, avoiding harmful products, drinking enough water and organizing a proper daily routine are the most important conditions.

National programs developed by the state, the activities of educational and health institutions that promote a healthy lifestyle should be further strengthened. For this, it is necessary to constantly hold seminars, trainings and mass media campaigns that promote a culture of healthy nutrition

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